

The effect of plant nutrition on water balance components and crop growth in rainfed lowland rice

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Rainfed lowland rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) occupies more than 40% of the total cultivated rice area in South and Southeast Asia (Maclean et al 2002). The total water supply and its distribution in space and time are mainly determined by the frequency and amount of rainfall, and topography. Options to manipulate this total water supply (e.g., through water harvesting) are limited. However, crop management interventions can affect water losses (e.g., runoff, evapotranspiration, seepage, percolation), but respective field studies from rainfed rice are rare. Therefore, the objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of plant nutrition on crop growth and water balance components in rainfed lowland rice. Improved nutrient supply was expected to reduce unproductive water losses and increase transpiration and related biomass formation.

A field experiment was conducted at the International Rice Research Institute (Los Baños, Philippines) from June to October in the 2006 wet season. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with five different fertilizer treatments (kg NPK ha⁻¹; T1: 0-0-0, T2: 40-8.8-0, T3: 80-17.6-0, T4: 120-26.4-0, T5: 0-0-49.8) and three replications for each treatment. Medium-duration (115–120 d) variety PSBRc9 was direct-seeded in rows with 0.2-m spacing after basal fertilizer application. The crop was strictly rainfed, except for one supplemental irrigation at flowering to avoid drought-induced spikelet sterility.

Rainfall was monitored at a nearby meteorological station (about 500 m away). Irrigation water quantity was measured with a flow meter. Soil water storage was monitored through soil sampling (0.2-m steps to 1-m depth, every second week) and gravimetric moisture content determination in all replications of T1 and T4. Groundwater depth was recorded daily in six piezometers, four in the corners and two on the longer side of the experimental field. Crop parameters recorded were leaf area index (LAI; measured once in 2 wk from a 0.125-m² area) and grain plus straw yield at harvest (grain yields were measured from a 5-m² area and straw yield was calculated from the harvest index determined from a 0.125-m² area and grain yield; grain yields were given at 14% moisture content). The LAI data from each treatment (average values of three

replications, every second week) were used to estimate evaporation and transpiration based on cumulative seasonal potential evapotranspiration (PET, calculated from the meteorological data using the Penman equation) and the assumption that evaporation becomes insignificant when the crop canopy closes at LAI of 3 (Tuong 1999).

During the growing period, cumulative rainfall (IRRI Climate Unit 2006) observed at the meteorological station was 713 mm for the early-harvested treatments (T3 and T4 at 108 d after emergence [DAE]) and 778 mm for the late-harvested treatments (T1, T2, and T5 at 113 DAE). The field was irrigated once at flowering stage and the amount of irrigation was 57 mm. Thus, total water input ranged between 770 and 835 mm.

Evaporation and transpiration were estimated as indicated in Figure 1a. In the initial development stage, transpiration changed from zero at seeding to 100% of PET when LAI became 3 (Tuong 1999). Then, transpiration remained at 100% of PET until the LAI again dropped below 3. After that and until harvest, transpiration decreased according to LAI development in the same way as that calculated in the initial stage, except that it did not decrease to zero. Evaporation responded in the opposite way. We assumed a linear LAI development between sampling points and a linear relation between LAI and transpiration/evaporation. It was also assumed that the soil surface was always close to saturation, allowing maximum evaporation according to PET.

Because the experimental site was located in the middle of a gentle slope, we assumed that belowground seepage into and out of the experimental field area was identical and did not constitute a water input or loss. Furthermore, the experimental field was banded and no surface runoff or run-on was observed during the cropping season. During most of the season, the field was not flooded and the water table fluctuated between 0.1- and 0.3-m depth. Shallow flooding (≤ 20 mm) of the whole experimental field occurred only at 14 d, scattered over the cropping season. Assuming that deep percolation occurred mainly during these periods and a percolation rate of 9 mm d^{-1} , which was observed in a neighboring irrigated field, the resulting total deep percolation was estimated at 126 mm. In rice, reported rates for deep percolation range from $1\text{--}5 \text{ mm d}^{-1}$ in heavy clay soils to $25\text{--}30 \text{ mm d}^{-1}$ in sandy and sandy loam soils (Tsubo et al 2005). The daily percolation rate used here fell within this range, given that the soil texture at the site was clay loam, and the soil was well structured and not puddled. The change in field water storage was calculated based on the soil water content in the soil profile to 1-m depth before the start of the experiment and at the end of the experiment. This calculation showed that soil water storage at the end of the experiment was 138 mm more than at the beginning. The analysis of soil water storage data in the soil profile (sampled once every 2 wk)

did not show statistical differences between T1 and T4 at any sampling date (data not shown). During the growing period, the cumulative PET derived from the meteorological station was 521 mm for treatments T3 and T4 (duration of 108 d) and 543 mm for T1, T2, and T5 (duration of 113 d). Table 1 gives an overview of all water balance components for each treatment, indicating a 28-mm surplus for treatments T1, T2, and T5, and a 15-mm deficit for treatments T3 and T4.

Table 1. Summary of all water balance components (in mm per season) for each fertilizer treatment and the whole cropping season in 2006.

Treatment	Inputs		Outputs				Balance (in – out)
	Rainfall	Irrigation	See- page	Deep percolation	PET	Change in soil water storage	
T1	778	57	0	126	543	138	28
T2	778	57	0	126	543	138	28
T3	713	57	0	126	521	138	-15
T4	713	57	0	126	521	138	-15
T5	778	57	0	126	543	138	28

As described above, LAI development was used to estimate the relative importance of transpiration and evaporation for each fertilizer treatment (Fig. 1b, Table 2). Cumulative PET was slightly lower in T3 and T4 because these treatments caused earlier crop maturity. Higher fertilizer rates had a huge effect on the relative distribution of cumulative transpiration and evaporation, and T3 more than doubled the transpiration in comparison with T1. This strong effect results from the higher LAI and its faster development, which reduces evaporation from below the canopy (Fig. 1b). The resulting higher water-use efficiency also had a significant effect on grain yield. The total biomass production at harvest was significantly correlated ($r^2 = 0.88$; $P < 0.01$) with transpiration (Fig. 2). The linear relation of transpiration and total biomass formation has been repeatedly described for several crops (Tanner and Sinclair 1983), indicating that the method used here to estimate cumulative transpiration produced realistic results. The slope of the regression line in Figure 2 represents the transpiration efficiency (TE) of the crop and corresponds to 2.5 g dry matter biomass per liter of water transpired. This compares with TE values of rice determined in pot experiments of 2.2 to 4.0 g dry matter per liter of water transpired (Haefele et al 2009).

LAI

Fig. 1. The relation between leaf area index (LAI) development and the relative importance of transpiration throughout the season (a) and LAI development for all treatments (b). DAE = days after emergence.

Fig. 2. Relation between estimated seasonal transpiration and total biomass production (oven dry weight of grain and straw) for all fertilizer treatments in the 2006 wet season.

Table 2. Treatment-dependent distribution of seasonal transpiration and evaporation, and observed grain yield (at 14% moisture content) and straw yield for the 2006 wet season.

Treatment	Cumulative seasonal PET ^a (mm)	Cumulative transpiration		Cumulative evaporation		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)
		(%)	(mm)	(%)	(mm)		
T1	543	33	177	67	366	2.28	3.54
T2	543	64	348	36	195	3.10	6.24
T3	521	76	395	24	126	3.70	8.35
T4	521	80	414	20	107	3.16	8.05
T5	543	58	312	42	231	2.82	4.83
CV (%)	–	–	–	–	–	0.01	0.02
LSD (0.05)	–	–	–	–	–	0.78	1.67

^aSeasonal potential evapotranspiration estimated using climate data and the Penman equation.

It can be concluded that improved crop nutrition can contribute significantly to improved water-use efficiency in rainfed environments, mainly by reducing evaporation and increasing transpiration.

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